

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER (NSCLC) IN SOUTH INDIA- EMPHASIS BETWEEN SMOKERS AND NON-SMOKERS

A. Rashmi, V.Manidhar, Dr. B.Rama

Mallareddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences (MRIPS)

[Affiliated To Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University Hyderabad (Jntuh)], Maisammaguda, Hyderabad Telangana- 500100.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 26/05/2020

Available online

03/07/2020

Keywords

Lung Cancer,
Histology Type,
Smoking,
Metastasis,
Adenocarcinoma.

ABSTRACT

Background- Lung cancer is one of the most aggressive, rapidly metastasizing and prevalent type of malignancy globally and is the major cause of morbidity and mortality. Aim- The study aims at analyzing the epidemiological patterns of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) in South India. Materials and methods- This is a retrospective analysis of prospectively collected data conducted at a government cancer hospital after the ethics committee clearance. The study was conducted for a duration of six months (October 2019 to March 2020). Required patient's data was collected from their case sheets. Obtained data was then entered and analyzed in SPSS. Results- 140 patients were included in the study, majority (70%) were males and 30% were females. The male: female ratio was 2.3:1. Large number of patients were within the age group of 41-60 years and about 63% were smokers and 37% were non-smokers. The most common type of histology was adenocarcinoma (60%) and common symptom at presentation was SOB in majority of patients. Statistically higher occurrence of all the histology types were seen in smokers than non-smokers. Bone followed by lung were the most common sites of metastases. A significant correlation was found between the adenocarcinoma histology among non-smokers and squamous cell histology among smokers. Most of the subjects were diagnosed in advanced stages (stage-4), thus treatment provided was mostly palliative in nature. Subjects with adenocarcinoma and with EGFR mutation were benefited when treated with Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor-Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitor (EGFR-TKI) Gefitinib. Conclusion- Smoking still remains the major risk factor. Males and smokers are at a higher risk of developing lung cancer when compared to females and non-smokers. Adenocarcinoma is the most commonly seen type of histology among non-smokers and squamous cell type of histology among smokers. Our study demonstrates the global shift of rise in adenocarcinoma histology in India. This information may help the clinicians for better understanding of the present scenario of the NSCLC histology epidemic which may further help in planning of better health care interventions.

Corresponding author

A. Rashmi

Department of Pharm-D.

Mallareddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences (MRIPS)

[Affiliated to JAWAHARLAL NEHRU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY HYDERABAD (JNTUH)]

Maisammaguda, Hyderabad Telangana.

anupozurashmi095@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **A. Rashmi et al. Epidemiology of Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (Nsclc) in South India-Emphasis Between Smokers and Non-Smokers. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2020:10(06).**

Copy right © 2020 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer is the major public health problem and is the leading cause of increased cancer-related morbidity and mortality worldwide [1]. It is the most prevalent and rapidly metastasizing type of cancer. According to the latest WHO statistics, 2.09 million cases of lung cancer have been reported in a year and 1.76 million deaths are due to lung cancer [2]. Its incidence and death pattern are due to smoking history primarily which is consistent for 20 or more years. Due to the evolving smoking patterns, social and cultural styles, which led to increasing rates of lung cancer in women [3].

Lung cancer is mainly of two subtypes, small-cell lung carcinoma (SCLC) and non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC), accounting for 15% and 85% respectively [4][5]. NSCLC is further classified into different histology types namely adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma and large cell carcinoma. Adenocarcinoma is the most common histology type in Asians which accounts for 40% of all lung cancer. It is seen more commonly in women and never-smokers [6]. The frequency of EGFR mutation is high in the Asia-Pacific adenocarcinoma subgroup and lowest frequency in Oceania adenocarcinoma subgroup [7]. Squamous cell carcinoma accounts for 25-30% of all lung cancers and the risk of developing this type increased by 7% per year of smoking. Thus, encouraging and bringing awareness in people for smoking prevention and cessation is very crucial especially in Indian population to reduce the lung cancer related incidence and mortality. A study by Ferkeich et al. reported that current smokers had poor survival rates when compared to non-smokers at the time of their diagnosis [8].

Lung cancer in never-smokers is also seen which is due to the other primary factors contributing in developing this condition including exposure to the radiation or asbestos, air pollution, genetics, second-hand smoking, occupational carcinogens [9]. Lung cancer is known to metastasize to specific sites like brain, bones, liver and adrenals. It can metastasize through lymphatic and blood vessels. Vascular invasion in resected lung carcinomas is commonly seen in low-stage tumors which eventually results in increased incidence of recurrence and decreased survival of patient [10]. Brain metastasis is a preferential site of metastasis in patients diagnosed with adenocarcinoma along with EGFR mutation and in many cases squamous cell carcinoma have a tendency to locally invade the thoracic wall [11][12]. The main objectives of the study are to evaluate the clinical profile and epidemiological patterns in non-small cell lung cancer patients with emphasis in the differences between smokers and non-smokers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a retrospective analysis of prospective data conducted in patients with a diagnosis of lung cancer at a government cancer hospital in Hyderabad, India. The study was conducted after the ethics committee clearance (Regd No: ECR/227/Inst/AP/2013/RR-16.) for a duration of six months between October 2019 and March 2020. Patient's data was collected from their case sheets and the demographic data, history of smoking, histology, metastasis, symptoms at presentation, place of residence, location of primary tumor, stage at presentation and details of the treatment were collected. Obtained data was then entered and analyzed in SPSS software version 26.

RESULTS

Total 140 Non-small cell lung cancer patients were included in our study. Data of these subjects was collected from a Govt. Oncology Hospital in Hyderabad between October 2019 and March 2020. A summary of the subject data is presented in the Table no. 1.

AGE

Subjects in the study are divided into three age groups. Within the 21-40 age group, non-smokers were more (88.9%) when compared to the smokers (11.1%). In the age group 41-60, 61.7% of the subjects were smokers and 38.3% were non-smokers. In >60 years age group, maximum number of subjects were smokers (74%) when compared to non-smokers (26%). The overall mean age \pm standard deviation was found to be 57.7 ± 10.7 . A significant association was found with presentation at younger age (20-40 yrs.) among non-smokers and presentation at an elder or advanced age (>60 yrs.) among smokers ($p=0.001$). The median age of non-smokers (56.5 years) was significantly lower when compared to the median age (60 years) of smokers ($p=0.015$).

Fig. 1, Graphical representation of subjects in different age groups.

Histology

Among the total 140 NSCLC subjects in our study, higher number of subjects were found diagnosed with adenocarcinoma (60%), followed by squamous cell carcinoma (37.1%) and large cell carcinoma (2.9%). Large number of subjects with adenocarcinoma are seen both in smokers and non-smokers.

Fig. 2, Pictorial representation of histology type.

Gender-

Of all the 140 subjects, 98 (70%) were males and 42 (30%) were females. Among smokers, males were more in number (n=79, 80.7%) and among the non-smokers, females were more (n=33, 78.6%). The male: female ratio was found to be 2.3:1.

Smoking status-

In our study, 63% of the total subjects were smokers and 37% of the total subjects were non-smokers. Thus, smokers are high in number. Among smokers, subjects include cigarette smokers, beedi smokers, ex-smokers and both cigarette and beedi smokers. Non-smokers are those who had no history of smoking at least once in their lifetime.

Presenting symptoms-

Patients were showing up different symptoms at presentation including SOB in maximum number of patients i.e. 99 (70.7%), followed by loss of weight and loss of appetite in 76 (54.3%) patients, chest pain (n=73, 52.1%), productive cough (n=54, 38.6%), non-productive cough (n=49, 35%), hemoptysis (16.4%), abdominal pain in 19 (13.6%) patients. Other symptoms like fever, weakness, dysphagia, digital clubbing, constipation, pedal edema, hoarseness of voice are seen in small number of patients. Symptoms also depend on the site of metastasis of the primary tumor at the time of presentation. In patients with bone metastasis, back ache and weakness of limbs are commonly seen and in patients with brain metastasis, symptoms like headache, seizures, facial swelling are most commonly presented by the patients.

Clinical staging-

Large number of patients were presented at advanced stage (stage-4) of the disease. 96 (56.6%) subjects out of 140 were diagnosed at stage-4 followed by 34 (24.3%) subjects at stage-3 and 10 (7.1%) subjects at stage-2.

Metastasis-

Metastasis is seen in large number of subjects in the study. 56 (40%) of the total subjects experienced metastasis of the primary tumor to the bone, followed by lung (20.7%), brain (12.9%), liver (12.1%) and adrenals (10%). In smokers, metastasis to lung, bone, brain, liver, adrenals are higher when compared to the non-smokers.

Location of tumor-

The primary location of the tumor in the subjects were found maximum in the right upper lobe (38.6%), followed by left lower (22.1%), left upper (20%), right lower (14.3%) and right middle (5%) lobes. Statistically higher occurrence of the tumor in the right upper, middle, lower and left upper lobes was seen in the smokers when compared to the non-smokers (p=0.085) at $\alpha=0.10$. The location of the tumor in the left lower lobe was seen high in non-smokers (51.6%) when compared to the smokers (48.4%).

Table no. 1, Patient details.

	Variables	Smokers	Non-smokers	p-value
No. of subjects		88	52	
Age (%)	20-40 years	11.1	88.9	p= .001*
	41-60 years	61.7	38.3	
	>60 years	74	26	
Median age		60	56.5	p= .015*
Gender (%)	Males	80.7	19.3	p= < .001*
	Females	21.4	78.6	
Place of residence (%)	Urban	67	33	Not significant
	Rural	55	45	
Clinical Symptoms (%)	SOB	60.6	39.4	Not significant
	Productive cough	66.6	33.4	
	Non-productive cough	53	47	
	Hemoptysis	61	39	
	LOA and LOW	56.6	43.4	
	Chest pain	60.3	39.7	
	Abdominal Pain	68.4	31.6	
Histopathology (%)	Adenocarcinoma	53.6	46.4	p= .02*
	Squamous cell	55	45	
	Large cell	75	25	
Stage (%)	II	50	50	Not significant
	III	73.5	26.5	
	IV	60.4	39.6	
Metastases sites (%)	Bone	60.8	39.2	Not significant
	Lung	62.1	37.9	
	Brain	50	50	
	Liver	53	47	
	Adrenals	50	50	
	Lymph nodes	69.4	30.6	
	Right upper	74.1	25.9	
Location of tumor (%)	Right middle	85.7	14.3	p= .085**
	Right lower	55	45	
	Left upper	57	43	
	Left lower	48.4	51.6	
Treatment given (%)	Palliative chemotherapy	61.2	38.8	
	Palliative RT	69.8	30.2	
	Chemo+ RT	69.6	30.4	
	Radical chemo	55.5	44.5	
	Neoadjuvant chemo	65	35	

*p<0.05, **p<0.10

Treatment received-

Majority of subjects were diagnosed with lung cancer in their advanced stages and thus large percent of these subjects received treatment that is palliative in nature. Patients with adenocarcinoma presenting at advanced stages (stage-3 and stage-4) and with Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) mutation showed good clinical response when treated with EGFR-Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitor i.e. Gefitinib. A significant number of subjects received neoadjuvant chemotherapy.

Histology, gender and smoking status correlation-

Our study concluded that, patients with squamous cell carcinoma type of histology were seen predominantly in male smokers (48.71%) and in females, this histology was seen among non-smokers ($p=0.0046$). In male non-smokers, type of histology seen in majority of the cases was adenocarcinoma (63%), followed by Squamous cell carcinoma (37%).

Although adenocarcinoma was the common histology seen in both smokers and non-smokers, it was found to occur more in non-smokers (75%) and squamous cell histology was found to occur among smokers (45.4%) ($p=0.006$).

Multinomial regression-

Multinomial logistic regression was performed for predicting smoking as a risk factor for the type of histology. It was found that, smokers are 2.96 times at a higher risk of developing Adenocarcinoma, 1.94 times at a higher risk of developing squamous cell carcinoma and 1.65 times at a higher risk of developing large cell carcinoma when compared to the non-smokers.

DISCUSSION

Lung cancer incidence is increasing fast in country like India. It is the main leading cause of mortality. Our study showed that sixty-three percentage of patients were smokers and thirty seven percent of patients were non-smokers. It is very similar to a study by Krishnamurthy A et al, where 60.4% were smokers and 39.5% were non-smokers [13], while in other study by H.Kaur et al, 76.9% were smokers and the 23% were non-smokers [14]. Thus higher percentage of smokers are diagnosed with lung cancer than the non-smokers.

Large number of subjects were within the age group of 41-60 years, followed by >60 years of age group. Small number of subjects were seen in 21-40 age group which is similar to the study by Jindal SK et al, in 1990 [15] where majority of the patients ($n=263$) were within the 41-60 age group, followed by >60 years and 21-40 years age group. Other studies by H.Kaur et al [14] and Jagdish Rawat et al [30], were parallel to our study where maximum number of subjects were within the 41-60 age group.

We found statistically significant differences with regard to age, gender, histopathology and location of tumor. However, no statistically significant differences were seen with regard to the place of residence, clinical symptoms, staging, metastases sites and the treatment provided to the patients.

The mean age in our study is 57.7 years. We found a significant association of presentation at younger age (20- 40 years) among non-smokers and presentation at elder age (>60 years) among smokers. The median age among smokers was 60 years which is statistically lower to the median age of non-smokers i.e. 56.5 years. Lung cancer was more prone to the male smokers when compared to male non-smokers and is seen high in non-smokers among the female gender. We noted a significant higher female lung cancer patients who are non-smokers, which is consistent with other studies by Jindal SK in Northern India [15], Gao YT et al, in China [16] and Toh CK et al in Japan [17]. The male to female sex ratio was found to be 2.3:1 which shows male predominance.

However, this high proportion of lung cancer in female non-smokers may be due to passive smoking or involuntary smoking, especially the partners of the male smokers are at higher risk. Many other factors may contribute to the development of lung cancer in non-smokers like environmental exposures including radon [18],

Arsenic [19], asbestos [20], estrogens [21], exposure to second-hand smoke [22], dusts and in patients with family history, genetic factors play an important role in the occurrence of lung cancer [23]. Exposure to indoor air toxins or wastes like the fumes, oil vapors during the cooking or frying and the fumes or smoke from the coal stoves especially in the women of rural regions of our country is also a major contributing risk factor for developing lung cancer [16][24].

Our study showed that the number of smokers from both rural and urban regions were high compared to the number of non-smokers from those regions. The percent of non-smokers especially females were more from the rural region which may be due to above mentioned reasons.

The most commonly seen symptoms in patients with NSCLC were cough which can be either productive or non-productive, shortness of breath (SOB), coughing up of blood or streaks of blood (hemoptysis), loss of weight and loss of appetite, chest pain, and abdominal pain. Our study showed no statistically significant difference in the clinical presentation of symptoms between smokers and non-smokers. However, the severity of these symptoms and the number of patients showing up these symptoms were found to be high among the smokers when compared to non-smokers which was consistent with the prior study by Noronha et al [25].

There is a shift in histopathologic distribution of NSCLC from the past three decades. In 1990s, squamous cell histology was most common type [26]. However, a research article in 2000 showed that there is increased incidence of adenocarcinoma [27]. In 2004, a review article stated that squamous cell histology was the most common type [28]. In 2006, an article published in China stated adenocarcinoma was more predominant [29], followed by in 2009 an article in India showed that Squamous cell histology was the most common type [30]. In the year 2012 [13] [25], 2016 [31] articles on the lung cancer were published which concluded that adenocarcinoma is the common histology type. Our study now is very much similar to the recent studies which showed adenocarcinoma (60%) is the most common type of histology followed by squamous cell (37%) and large cell carcinoma (3%). Thus, the results state a shift in histology in India from squamous cell carcinoma to adenocarcinoma. The first person to state this shift of histology was by Devesa et al in 2005 [32]. The reason for the shift of histology from squamous cell to adenocarcinoma is due to the changes in the process of cigarette manufacture and the changes of cigarette smoking behavior, with the switch of unfiltered cigarettes to filtered ones which allows alteration in the depth of inhalation in some people. Smoke from these filtered cigarettes maybe inhaled deeply leading to the deposition of carcinogens peripherally causing adenocarcinoma histology [33] [34] [35].

Statistically significant association was found with squamous cell carcinoma histology between male smokers and female non-smokers. We also found a significant association of adenocarcinoma histology in non-smokers and squamous cell carcinoma in smokers which is similar to the study [13].

Multinomial regression was done to identify if smoking is a risk factor for causing lung cancer and at what rate the smokers are at a risk compared to the non-smokers in developing this condition of high mortality and morbidity. It was found from the result that smokers are at a higher risk of developing squamous cell carcinoma and large cell carcinoma and the risk rate doubled for developing of adenocarcinoma which is consistent with a prior study [36].

Our study also reported that a statistically higher occurrence of primary tumor location is the right upper lobe in smokers followed by the left upper lobe. Least number of patient results showed the location of the tumor in the right middle lobe. In non-smokers, maximum cases showed tumor in the left lower followed by the right upper lobes.

Large number of patients are being diagnosed at advanced stages (stage-3 and 4). Even in our study, majority of smokers and non-smokers are diagnosed in stage 4 (56.6%) and stage 3 (24.3%). This late diagnosis is maybe due to misdiagnosis of the patients with Tuberculosis (TB), as the symptoms like chest pain, hemoptysis, cough, shortness of breath and radiological findings for both lung cancer and TB are almost similar. These patients are initiated with Anti-Tubercular treatment (ATT). This misdiagnosis as TB in developing countries like India would lag the time period between onset of symptoms and actual diagnosis and thus the patients are in advanced stages or the disease have been progressed already by the time of diagnosis and eventually initiation of appropriate treatment for these patients is also delayed [37] [38]. In contrast to these studies, another study stated that increased delay between the symptom and treatment initiation gave significant data for a better prognosis and shorter delay time is associated with bad prognosis of the patient [39].

The treatment provided to patients in the study was palliative in nature for maximum number of subjects. This is because most of the subjects are in advanced stages. Radiotherapy is done primarily in patients with metastasis to bone, lung in our subjects. Patients with adenocarcinoma presenting in advanced stages (stage 3 and 4) and with epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) gene mutations, showed good clinical response when treated with Gefitinib which is an EGFR-TKI (EGFR- Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitor). The superior action of Gefitinib as primary treatment for adenocarcinoma subjects with EGFR gene mutation is also stated in other studies [40] [41] [42]. However many studies reported that the overall survival of never-smokers with NSCLC is superior when compared to the smokers with NSCLC. In contrast to this, a study by Subramanian J et al, concluded that there is no significant difference in survival between never-smokers and smokers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study suggests that the incidence of lung cancer in never smokers is increasing and smoking is a major risk factor in men for causing the condition. In some cases, lung cancer is being misdiagnosed as tuberculosis which is causing delay in the diagnosis and treatment of cancer. Thus, effective measures to detect the cancer at an early stage is needed. The interesting part of our study is that the present global shift of histology from squamous cell carcinoma to adenocarcinoma is seen which is different from quondam studies showing squamous cell carcinoma as the most common histology type. This information may help the clinicians for better understanding of the present scenario of the NSCLC histology epidemic which may further help in planning of better health care interventions. Future research on this shift of histology type and the changes in epidemiological patterns is required.

Conflict of interest-

There were no conflicts of interest among the authors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank MNJ Government Cancer Hospital authorities for providing complete support and guidance during the collection and interpretation of data.

REFERENCES

1. Siegel RL, Miller KD, Jemal A. Cancer statistics, 2019. *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians*. 2019; 69(1): 7-34.
2. Cancer key facts [homepage on the Internet]. World Health Organization [updated 2018 Sep 12]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cancer>
3. Barta JA, Powell CA, Wisnivesky JP. Global epidemiology of lung cancer. *Annals of global health*. 2019; 85(1).
4. Sher T, Dy GK, Adjei AA. Small cell lung cancer. *Mayo Clin Proc*. 2008; 83:355-67.
5. Zappa C, Mousa SA. Non-small cell lung cancer: current treatment and future advances. *Translational lung cancer research*. 2016; 5(3): 288.
6. T.Y. D. Cheng, S. M. Cramb, P. D. Baade, D. R. Youlden, C. Nwogu, M. E. Reid. The international epidemiology of lung cancer: latest trends, disparities, and tumor characteristics. *Journal of Thoracic Oncology* 2016; vol. 11: 1653–1671.
7. A. Midha, S. Dearden, and R. McCormack. EGFR mutation incidence in non-small-cell lung cancer of adenocarcinoma histology: a systematic review and global map by ethnicity (mutMapII). *American Journal of Cancer Research* 2015; vol. 5: 2892–2911.
8. Ferketich AK, Niland JC, Mamet R, Zornosa C, D'Amico TA, Ettinger DS, et al. Smoking status and survival in the national comprehensive cancer network non-small cell lung cancer cohort. *Cancer*. 2013; 119(4): 847-53.
9. J. M. Samet, E. Avila-Tang, P. Boffetta et al. Lung cancer in never smokers: clinical epidemiology and environmental risk factors. *Clinical Cancer Research* 2009; vol. 15: 5626–5645.
10. Gabor S, Renner H, Popper H, Anegg U, Sankin O, Matzi V, et al. Invasion of blood vessels as significant prognostic factor in radically resected T1-3N0M0 non-small- cell lung cancer. *European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery*. 2004; 25: 439–442.
11. Hendriks LE, Smit EF, Vosse BA, Mellema WW, Heideman DA, Bootsma GP, et al. EGFR mutated non-small cell lung cancer

- patients: more prone to development of bone and brain metastases? *Lung Cancer*. 2014; 84: 86–91.
12. Wilbertz T, Wagner P, Petersen K, Stiedl AC, Scheble VJ, Maier S, et al. SOX2 gene amplification and protein overexpression are associated with better outcome in squamous cell lung cancer. *Modern Pathology*. 2011; 24: 944–953.
 13. Krishnamurthy A, Vijayalakshmi R, Gadigi V, Ranganathan R, Sagar TG. The relevance of "Nonsmoking-associated lung cancer" in India: A single-centre experience. *Indian journal of cancer*. 2012; 49(1): 82-8.
 14. Kaur H, Sehgal IS, Bal A, Gupta N, Behera D, Das A, et al. Evolving epidemiology of lung cancer in India: Reducing non-small cell lung cancer-not otherwise specified and quantifying tobacco smoke exposure are the key. *Indian journal of cancer*. 2017; 54(1): 285.
 15. Jindal SK, Behera D. Clinical spectrum of primary lung cancer: Review of Chandigarh experience of 10 years. *Lung India* 1990; 8: 94-8.
 16. Gao YT, Blot WJ, Zheng W, Ersnow AG, Hsu CW, Levin LI, et al. Lung cancer among Chinese women. *International journal of cancer*. 1987; 40(5): 604-9.
 17. Toh CK, Gao F, Lim WT, Leong SS, Fong KW, Yap SP, et al. Never-smokers with lung cancer: epidemiologic evidence of a distinct disease entity. *Journal of clinical oncology*. 2006; 24(15): 2245-51.
 18. Darby S, Hill D, Auvinen A, Barros-Dios JM, Baysson H, Bochicchio F, et al. Radon in homes and risk of lung cancer: Collaborative analysis of individual data from 13 European case-control studies. *BMJ* 2005; 330:223.
 19. Chen CL, Hsu LI, Chiou HY, Hsueh YM, Chen SY, Wu MM, et al. Ingested arsenic, cigarette smoking, and lung cancer risk: A follow-up study in arseniasis-endemic areas in Taiwan. *JAMA* 2004; 292: 2984-90.
 20. Van Loon AJ, Kant IJ, Swaen GM, Goldbohm RA, Kremer AM, van den Brandt PA. Occupational exposure to carcinogens and risk of lung cancer: Results from The Netherlands cohort study. *Occup Environ Med* 1997; 54: 817-24.
 21. Wu CT, Chang YL, Shih JY, Lee YC. The significance of estrogen receptor beta in 301 surgically treated non-small cell lung cancers. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg* 2005; 130: 979-86.
 22. Brennan P, Buffler PA, Reynolds P, Wu AH, Wichmann HE, Agudo A, et al. Secondhand smoke exposure in adulthood and risk of lung cancer among never smokers: A pooled analysis of two large studies. *Int J Cancer* 2004; 109: 125-31.
 23. Gorlova OY, Zhang Y, Schabath MB, Lei L, Zhang Q, Amos CI, et al. Never smokers and lung cancer risk: A case-control study of epidemiological factors. *Int J Cancer* 2006; 118: 1798-804.
 24. Yu IT, Chiu YL, Au JS, Wong TW, Tang JL. Dose-response relationship between cooking fumes exposures and lung cancer among Chinese nonsmoking women. *Cancer Res* 2006; 66: 4961-7.
 25. Noronha V, Dikshit R, Raut N, Joshi A, Pramesh CS, George K, et al. Epidemiology of lung cancer in India: Focus on the differences between non-smokers and smokers: A single-centre experience. *Indian J Cancer* 2012; 49: 74-81.
 26. Dr. Jindal SK, Behera D. Clinical spectrum of primary lung cancer: Review of Chandigarh experience of 10 years. *Lung India* 1990; 8: 94-8.
 27. Kreuzer M, Kreienbrock L, Müller KM, Gerken M, Wichmann E. Histologic types of lung carcinoma and age at onset. *Cancer: Interdisciplinary International Journal of the American Cancer Society*. 1999 May; 85(9): 1958-65.
 28. Behera D, Balamugesh T. Lung cancer in India. *Indian Journal of Chest Diseases and Allied Sciences*. 2004; 46: 269-82.
 29. Ignatius TS, Chiu YL, Au JS, Wong TW, Tang JL. Dose-response relationship between cooking fumes exposures and lung cancer among Chinese nonsmoking women. *Cancer research*. 2006; 66(9): 4961-7.
 30. Rawat J, Sindhvani G, Gaur D, Dua R, Saini S. Clinico-pathological profile of lung cancer in Uttarakhand. *Lung India: official organ of Indian Chest Society*. 2009; 26(3): 74.
 31. Bala S, Gundeti S, Linga VG, Maddali LS, Digumarti RR, Uppin SG. Clinicopathological features and outcomes in advanced non-small cell lung cancer with tailored therapy. *Indian journal of medical and paediatric oncology: official journal of Indian Society of Medical & Paediatric Oncology*. 2016; 37(4): 242.
 32. Devesa SS, Bray F, Vizcaino AP, Parkin DM. International lung cancer trends by histologic type: male: female differences diminishing and adenocarcinoma rates rising. *International journal of cancer*. 2005; 117(2): 294-9.
 33. Furrukh M. Tobacco smoking and lung cancer: perception-changing facts. *Sultan Qaboos University Medical Journal*. 2013; 13(3): 345.
 34. Stellman SD, Muscat JE, Thompson S, Hoffmann D, Wynder EL. Risk of squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma of the lung in relation to lifetime filter cigarette smoking. *Cancer* 1997; 80: 382-8.
 35. Thun MJ, Lally CA, Flannery JT, Calle EE, Flanders WD, Heath CW Jr. Cigarette smoking and changes in the histopathology of lung cancer. *J Natl Cancer Inst* 1997; 89: 1580-6.
 36. Yang P, Cerhan JR, Vierkant RA, Olson JE, Vachon CM, Limburg PJ, et al. Adenocarcinoma of the lung is strongly associated with cigarette smoking: further evidence from a prospective study of women. *American journal of epidemiology*. 2002; 156(12): 1114-22.
 37. Singh VK, Chandra S, Kumar S, Pangtey G, Mohan A, Guleria R. A common medical error: lung cancer misdiagnosed as sputum negative tuberculosis. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2009; 10: 335-8.
 38. Chandra S, Mohan A, Guleria R, Singh V, Yadav P. Delays during the diagnostic evaluation and treatment of lung cancer. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev* 2009; 10: 453-6.
 39. Myrdal G, Lambe M, Hillerdal G, Lamberg K, Agustsson T, Ståhle E. Effect of delays on prognosis in patients with non-small cell lung cancer. *Thorax*. 2004; 59: 45–9
 40. Mok TS, Wu YL, Thongprasert S, Yang CH, Chu DT, Saijo N, et al. Gefitinib or carboplatin–paclitaxel in pulmonary adenocarcinoma. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2009; 361(10): 947-57.

41. Lynch TJ, Bell DW, Sordella R, Gurubhagavatula S, Okimoto RA, Brannigan BW, et al. Activating mutations in the epidermal growth factor receptor underlying responsiveness of non-small-cell lung cancer to gefitinib. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2004; 350(21): 2129-39.
42. Griffin R, Ramirez RA. Molecular Targets in Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer. *Ochsner Journal*. 2017; 17(4): 388-92.

54878478451200521

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

